

Turkey – Syria earthquake of 6 February 2023

Preseismic Displacement Map from Sentinel-1 Imagery

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This report describes a preliminary remote sensing analysis of the preseismic ground velocity map and the relative displacement time series applying the multi-temporal InSAR approach in Turkey.

Sentinel-1 images, provided by the European Space Agency, along the descending orbit (Track 21) were processed to derive a map retrieved by applying the MT-InSAR approach named Small Baseline Subset (SBAS, Berardino et al., 2002). 147 SAR images (TOPSAR acquisition mode) were selected and the temporal span covered is 20180107-20230129 and resulting in 419 pairs.

A multilook factor of 24x6 along the range and azimuth direction was applied resulting in a final ground pixel equal to about 90m x 90m. The SRTM Digital Elevation Model (30 meters) was used to remove the topographic contribution. The Goldstein filter (Goldstein et al., 1998) was used with a value of 0.5. Then the Single Value Decomposition method was applied to invert the interferogram data stack.

A reference point in a stable zone was selected to which refer the retrieved results. The obtained outputs were geocoded in the WGS84 reference system.

The used processing chain was provided by ESA through the GeoExploitation Platform (GEP, <https://geohazards-tep.eu/#!>) and the specific P-SBAS service by IREA-CNR.

Figure 1. Mean ground velocity map from S1 descending data (20180107-20230129).

The retrieved map (Fig.1) shows the mean ground velocity affecting the area earlier the two catastrophic earthquakes (yellow stars in the figure) occurred in the region on February 6 2023. None evident pattern close to the fault is visible even if further analysis has to be performed observing the relative displacement time series.

Nevertheless, observing to the south-west clear subsidence patterna are highlighted along the coastline close to Alessandretta city and to the Antiochia surroundings as well (Fig.2).

Figure 2. Displacement time series close to the city of Antiochia (Syria).

References

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